

Title: Impact of Demonetization – A Study with reference to Street Vendors

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Abstract: Demonetization is the progression in which a particular currency or valuable mineral is degraded as a legal tender to avoid some illegal practices and also make a revolution relevant for economic welfare. Demonetization happens when a particular currency is no longer in regular use within the country of origin, or when a newer currency comes into circulation with the view to make regulations for better functioning. The latest demonetization in India was the sudden announcement by Prime Minister of India dated 8th November at 8.30 p.m. that 500 and 1,000 rupees currency notes would not be legal tender from midnight of 8th November 2016. The announcement was made much after banking hour's thus giving nobody a chance for any foul play and at the same time making alternative actions to avoid public sufferings.

The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) data suggests that the proportion of 500 and 1,000 rupees currency notes were 86.4% of total value of notes in circulation on March 31, 2016, amounting to 14 trillion. A significant portion of old currency was also considered to be fake money pumped into the economy to fund terrorist activities that are supported by illegitimate groups. At the stroke of midnight of 8th November 2016, India lost 86.4% of its monetary base. In this single move, the Government has attempted to tackle the issues arising from various areas that affect the economy, i.e., counterfeit currency in circulation and terror financing. The Government's move to introduce the 2,000 rupees currency notes to ease the short money fall has not helped the economy as expected. Thus, street vendors had been carrying a significant currency demanding for small payments, which is inappropriate for exchange. Both Large, Small and Medium scale traders and public people too suffered a lot to carry monetary transactions. Though, IT has been enrolling in financial transactions like Net Banking, E-wallet, E-commerce and so on. It does not exercise among illiterate people. Thus, the study aims at understanding the impacts of demonetization on the street vendors and the changes happened in their day-to-day transaction and innovative ideas undertaken to overcome these issues.

Key words: Demonetization, street vendors, Long-run surviva